
CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY MANAGEMENT

BY CHETAN SACHDEVA¹

ABSTRACT

CSR is an important which contributes to economic development and improves the quality of the work-life balance. There are other nomenclatures of CSR. Companies are focusing on some areas like education, agriculture etc. CSR is completely different from charity as there can be a charity without CSR but there can be no business without CSR. There can be so many dimensions of CSR but it depends on company to company, like what are their primary goals. Strategic approaches are the ones that can help in implementing CSR projects in various companies such as the Co-ordination approach which ensures that the company and employees must co-ordinate with each other for the better result of the CSR project. In CSR policy there must be a vision clause, an objectives clause as well as proper monetary and governance mechanisms. SOP stands for the standard operating procedure, there should be SOP for each expertise in a CSR project. There are 2 types of social research methods and this type of research is conducted by social scientists. SROI stands for social return on investment and it is a way of expressing outcome in relation to investment. It's about tracking and qualifying changes. CSR can be done through various departments such as HR, safety, marketing and many more. CSR was introduced the first time in the Companies Act, 2013 and then, the Company (CSR) Policy, 2014 rules were made. Section 135 of the Companies Act, 2013 deals with various things of CSR.

Keywords: CSR, Companies Act, 2013, Approaches, Policy, Social Research and Charity.

¹ Author is a student at UPES, Dehradun

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a way for companies to include social and environmental concerns in how they do business and interact with others. It's like making sure a company balances making money, taking care of the environment, and being socially responsible.² This is often called the "**Triple-Bottom-Line-Approach.**" CSR isn't just about charity or giving money – it's a strategic way for companies to manage their business while meeting the expectations of shareholders and stakeholders. While charity and philanthropy are good, CSR goes a step further by integrating social and environmental responsibility into the core of how a company operates.³

A. Other Nomenclature in CSR

- 1). Trusteeship of wealth – How to share the corporate wealth to the society.
- 2). Corporate citizen – as a citizen of corporate society they have some responsibilities and duties towards each other and the company.
- 3). Corporate sustainability – Business has to be sustainable in long run.

B. Areas on which companies are focusing on:

- * Physical/mental health.
- * Education.
- * Women Empowerment.
- * Agriculture Development Programme.
- * Infrastructure Development Programme.
- * Charity.

C. D/W CSR & Charity

There can be business without charity, there can be charity without business but there can be no business without CSR.

² UCHE EWELUKWA OFODILE, SARAH ALTSCHULLER, ANNA DOLIZE, And ICHEAL FESSLER, CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITIES 183 (Spring 2012).

³ United Nation Industrial Development Organization, [https://www.unido.org/our-focus/advancing-economic-competitiveness/competitive-trade-capacities-and-corporate-responsibility/corporate-social-responsibility-market-integration/what-csr#:~:text=Corporate%20Social%20Responsibility%20is%20a,and%20interactions%20with%20their%20stakeholders,\(last visited Nov. 17, 2023\).](https://www.unido.org/our-focus/advancing-economic-competitiveness/competitive-trade-capacities-and-corporate-responsibility/corporate-social-responsibility-market-integration/what-csr#:~:text=Corporate%20Social%20Responsibility%20is%20a,and%20interactions%20with%20their%20stakeholders,(last%20visited%20Nov.%2017,%202023).)

D. Strategic approaches to implement CSR project

- 1). **Catelitic approach** – Company put some money on CSR project and in return expect the extra profit from employees.
- 2). **Co-ordination** – To ensure proper implementation of CSR project the company must have to coordinate with various departments and stakeholders.
- 3). **Professional** – How better is the plan, what are the stages of implementation, how it will tackle all the ground problems and many more.
- 4). **Participatory** – A company must have to participate in those CSR project which does not even fall under their expertise.⁴

E. Development of CSR policy

- *Vision statement
- *CSR mission
- *CSR policy objectives
- * Applicability to whom and till what extent
- * Engagement of stakeholder (Identified)
- * Process of CSR
- * Philosophy statement
- * Complete description of Governance system of CSR project
- * Social causes
- * Targets to be achieved
- * Monetary mechanism
- * Impact assessment⁵

F. SOP Development (Standard operating development)

- * Background & reason
- * Scope
- * Objectives
- * Stakeholder engagement

⁴ *Supra note 3.*

⁵ NEIL MITCHEL, CORPORATE POWER, LEGITIMACY AND SOCIAL POLICY 201 (Western Political Quarterly 1986).

- * Roles & responsibilities
- * Beneficiaries

G. Designing a CSR project

Ten-point rule to launch a CSR programme

- * Defines the name of CSR project
- * Understanding the benefit
- * Get top management buy in for the programme
- * Establish long-term vision
- * Explore opportunities as per your mission
- * Establish good relation with community
- * Schedule meeting with community
- * Set-up monitoring and evaluation framework
- * Re-designing project
- * Impact assessment

H. Project purpose outline

- * Project summary
- * Objectives
- * Rational – reason to proposed, importance & many more
- * Activities
- * Community participation plan
- * Project work plan
- * Monitoring plan
- * Sustainability
- * Budget details
- * Name, sign & date (official seal)

I. Social Return on Investment (SROI)⁶

⁶ *Supra note 3.*

SROI is a way of expressing outcome in relation to investment. It's about tracking and qualifying changes.

SROI – Value of outcome/Investment

*** SROI Approaches**

- 1). Philanthropic – Donating things for the welfare of public at large.
- 2). Commercial – Business looks for short term & long-term interest.
- 3). Compliance – The companies are bound to follow the rules & regulation.

*** Types**

- 1). Evaluated – Based on actual outcome in given period.
- 2). Forecasted – Predict how much social value will be created if the activities meet their intend objectives.

*** Principles**

- * Involve stakeholder
- * Understood what changes
- * Value the thing that matter
- * Only include what is material
- * Do not over claim
- * Be transparent
- * Verify the result

J. CSR Activities

CSR through HR department

- * Financial support – Scholarship through CSR program
- * Proper guidance in terms of education
- * Provide counselling classes⁷

CSR through safety

⁷ *Supra* note 3.

* Companies should taught safety measures at the age of 40 to 50 but it should be start from childhood.

* They should also conduct seminars in schools, colleges and many more.

CSR through marketing

* To show how to use the product properly (it will increase the sale).

K. International forums on CSR

- 1). Sustainable Development Goals till 2030.
- 2). UN Global Compact (principles).
- 3). Global Reporting Initiative.
- 4). UN Guiding Principles on Business & Human Rights.
- 5). OECD Guidelines.⁸

L. CSR Laws in India

- * India is the first Country to mandate to form a CSR committee.
- * Company has to reserve 2% profit from the last 3 years for CSR.
- * CSR committee should contain 3 directors and atleast 1 should be independent director.
- * CSR policy should be on public website.⁹

M. The Company (CSR) Policy, 2014

1). Section 135 (1) of Companies Act, 2013¹⁰ – A company having:

- * Net worth – Rs. 500 Cr. Or more
- * Turnover – Rs. 1000 Cr. Or more
- * Net profit – Rs. 5 Cr. Or more

*It is mandatory for the above companies to make a CSR committee

⁸ UCHE EWELUKWA OFODILE, SARAH ALTSCHULLER, ANNA DOLIZE, And ICHEAL FESSLER, CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITIES 183 (Spring 2012).

⁹ MINISTRY OF CORPORATE AFFAIRS, https://www.mca.gov.in/mca/html/mcav2_en/home/actsandrules/companies+act++2013/companiesact2013.html#:~:text=The%20Act%20consolidates%20and%20amends,1956%20is%20still%20in%20force (last visited 21 Nov. 2023).

¹⁰ The Companies Act 2013, § 135(1), No. 18, Acts of Parliament, 2013 (India).

N. Exceptions

- 1). Section 2 (42) - Private company with only 2 Directors on board shall constitute CSR committee with two such Directors.¹¹
- 2). Foreign companies with 2 Directors shall form a CSR committee but one director must be resident of India.
- 3). Section 135 (2) – Report under section 134 to disclose the composition of the CSR committee.
- 4). Section 135 (3) - CSR committee recommend the board about policies, expenditures and many more.
- 5). Section 135 (4) – Board will approve the recommended policy.
- 6). Section 135 (5) – Board shall ensure atleast 2% of Net Profit is should be reserved for CSR.
- 7). Schedule VII – The objectives of CSR policies should be written in specific manner like – Education, gender equality, environment and many more.¹²
- 8). Section 8 – Any corpus under this section is covered in CSR expenditure.¹³

¹¹ The Companies Act 2013, § 2(42), No. 18, Acts of Parliament, 2013 (India).

¹² The Companies Act 2013, Schedule VII, No. 18, Acts of Parliament, 2013 (India).

¹³ The Companies Act 2013, § 8, No. 18, Acts of Parliament, 2013 (India).